

The Relationship between Culture and Ecosystem as Reflected in Assamese Folklore

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In simple terms 'culture' is defined as the integrated pattern of human knowledge, belief and behaviour that depends upon the capacity for symbolic thoughts, actions and social learning. It is the set of shared attitudes, values, goals and practices that characterize an institution, organization or group. In the twentieth century, when the term 'culture' started attracting anthropological attention, it was seen as something that encompasses all human phenomenon that are not purely the results of human genetics. Anthropology defines 'culture' in two ways:

1. As the evolved human capacity to classify and represent experiences with symbols and to act imaginatively and creatively.
2. As the distinct ways in which people living in different parts of the world classified and represented their experiences and acted creatively.

For this paper, 'culture' will be understood not only as a knowledge-system, but also as an inclusive process which is always in a state of flux. In the process of transforming culture, human beings, over the process of evolution, have discovered more and more ways of capturing and harnessing energy from the environment. In this line, the proponent of Cultural Ecology, Julian Steward maintained that any culture is not less or more evolved than another; rather they have adapted differently to different environments. Thus, each society has its own cultural history.

The central argument in Cultural Ecology studies is that natural environment is one of the major contributors to the social organization and culture-building of the societies that are dependent upon it. In other words, the ecological locale plays a significant role in shaping the culture of a region. Also, the adaptation to the changing environment induces

culture changes. Julian Steward introduces a simple methodology to study culture in this light. Firstly, it looks at the methods used by human beings to exploit the environment to get a living out of it. Then it identifies the common patterns of human behavior that are associated with making use of the environment. With thus identified common patterns in various cultures, attempts are made to assess how much these patterns of behavior influence other aspects of culture.

The focus here would be on two features,

1. How an environment impacts and shapes a culture.
2. How human beings impact on the habitat and make a cultural landscape through culture-building.

Although ecology stands as a determining factor especially to folk cultures, it is important to note that no two cultures are identical, despite a similar ecological setting. This indicates that each group of people employs its unique strategies to survive in its natural setting. Folk groups are more involved with their physical environment and therefore they establish an intimate relationship with nature. And, more importantly, their adaptive strategies to the environment are based on sustainability. This essentially describes how they use nature and consume energy in a way that does not destroy the environment. Their interactions with surrounding habitats are intense and singular as they have to depend directly on nature for their livelihood in different ways-- farming, herding, hunting, and fishing, etc. to name a few. Therefore, various religious acts to worship nature—in gratitude for being the Giver and in fear for being the Snatcher have

found place in folk cultures. The examples of their love, fear and the sense of peaceful co-existence are found in their folktales that inevitably have 'nature' as a central character, proverbs that are charged with wisdom about weather and agriculture, and in their traditional architecture. The effort to balance livelihood with the climate and available resources is an important characteristic of folk life. Folk religion also suggests ways to control and modify nature.

Thus, a direct relationship is formed between nature and human beings (and hence, culture). The habitat influences the formation of culture and culture acts as a means to celebrate as well as control nature. Also, the folks too shape the landscape through their culture-building. This is seen even at a level as small as that of a household. Human beings consciously and purposefully form their geographical environment, and their decisions about living space arrangement are motivated by their vital needs.

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As mentioned earlier, the intense relationship that the human beings share with the surrounding environment, determines culture to a certain extent. The folk knowledge that is stored in the folklores is the result of ages of face-to-face encounters and interactions with nature. This folk knowledge is futuristic in the sense all the folklore items teach how to respect nature as an omnipotent being and as something on which the human beings will have to go on depending no matter how much any civilization progresses. Religion and folklore are the results of such knowledge acquired through direct interactions with nature.

Folklore of Assam being the factor in focus in this paper, the discussion should necessarily be preceded by an introduction to some examples from the folk life of Assam that have influenced this factors.

Effects of Ecology on Folk-life

The earliest interactions of human beings with nature started as soon as they started existing; food and shelter being the earliest requirements of human beings. When farming was invented as a means of earning livelihood, these interactions with nature became more dependent as well as controlling. In Assam, the major livelihood means is agriculture; fishing, hunting and depending on wildlife being some livelihood measures of some minor tribes. Therefore, the choice of places to settle down depended on the preferred livelihood measures and the availability of the resources.

Together with different livelihood measures their dwelling processes also depend on the climatic conditions and available resources. The folk-architecture is planned according to the nature of the land and natural calamities that this region is prone to. The land of this state of Assam consists of both plains as well as hills, and both kinds of lands are populated with different tribes and groups of people. The innumerable number of rivers in this region results in yearly floods creating havoc in the people's lives. These factors result in the existence of various architectural ways of dealing with nature; *Chang-ghors* being a popular architectural form, with the touch of distinctive folk-beliefs, among different groups of people. Most of the houses are built with the available natural resources, that is, bamboo or wood, earth and hay.

The major deciding factor in the distinctive dress-codes of every tribe and folk group is the weather condition. The tribes from relatively colder mountains wear clothes that are completely different from those of the hotter plains. Also, the availability of certain resources decides the texture of the clothes, while the perception of nature that is distinctive of any folk group decides the motifs used and woven in the clothes. Thus, in all the basic aspects of the lifestyle of the tribes and different folk groups of Assam, as in all other societies, the impact of nature is inevitably seen.

Effects of Folk-life on Ecology

As mentioned earlier, as soon as human beings started to consume natural resources for their day-to-day necessities, they started to exercise some sort of control and power over other habitats. Their dependence started to be mutual. As they discovered newer ways of farming, they started to use nature in their own innovative ways. These often caused disturbances in the ecosystem as man also tried to arrange the resources as per their convenience; a major example being the preparation for the *Jhum* cultivation which is a common way of farming among the hill-tribes of Assam and neighbouring states.

The arrangement of living space and the creation of landscape at a smaller level are characteristic to every civilized society. The landscape of a household is decided by man not as per the natural setting. Man first tended to make the best out of nature for a better household landscape with his characteristic aesthetic sense, which gradually got influenced by certain folk beliefs and further got influenced by other determining factors such as availability of space and growth of population and so on. Thus, earlier view of using nature for the mutual best got transformed into using it for dire necessity. Assam is not much urbanized yet, and thus retains much of its natural space intact and unpolluted by aggressive human means to use nature.

Commercialization of natural resources also affected the ecosystem for better or for worse. In Assam, commercialization of natural resources started with the tea-gardens; tea being a migrant produce that was forced into the Assamese ecosystem and locale which however adopted it for the better. The next huge resource that had been commercialized in Assam is oil. This, however, acted not only as an attempt to get the best out of nature for human comfort, but also as disturbances to the neighbouring ecosystem.

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The folklore of Assam has immense references to the folk's contact, dependence and fear for nature. The folktales and myths cite examples of the folks' awe of nature and their realization of the fact that their lives and living depended on nature. Their world-view was acquired out of the intense co-relationship shared with nature.

This world view influenced the creation of myths that are symbolic of greater truths that are characteristic realizations and beliefs specific to a specific group of people. Myths, and the awe of nature made way for folk religions, religious practices and magic.

Some tribes in Assam such as the Adis and the Mishings believe that they have originated from the Moon God and Sun Goddess. For the Adis, Doini, i.e. Sun and Polo, i.e. Moon are the supreme gods, in contrary to the Aryan religions. These people recognize Sun and Moon as the supreme source of energy for their livelihood and fear to provoke their anger. Tree worship, Cow worship, Water or River worship, Crop worship, Evil deity and spirit worship, Illness worship etc. are some of the earliest examples of the formation of folk-religions. The 'awe' factor ruled the folk-imagination immensely in their day-to-day encounters with nature, resulting in their worshipping of different natural objects (1). as life-givers, (2). as heroes to protect the people and (3). as evils to keep themselves away from harming the people.

A myth from the simple illiterate Bodos describe the origin of human beings in universe which more or less go in the lines of present scientific research. They believe, "Bhagawan Aham Guru created two birds, a male and a female. The female bird laid three eggs. Thousands of years rolled by, but the eggs did not hatch. So the female bird broke one egg. There was no sign of chicks. Aham Guru forbade her from further breaking of eggs and asked her to scatter the broken egg from which subsequently were created evil spirits, worms, insects and trees. Then, after thousands of years, from the remaining two eggs were born human beings." Some tribes such as the Deuris and the Tangsas believe that in the early days there was only water all around and the God from the heaven created earth and the living beings by employing different factors to create and populate it. These different factors at times were Sun and Moon, at times some Bird, at times a flower or wind and so on, which was decided by whatever 'object of awe' that the particular tribe sees or experiences in their day-to-day life and surrounding environment.

The farming people invented ways of invoking nature to create a fertile soil for their crops to grow, which was decided by the knowledge about nature that the particular folk group acquired through its encounters with nature. They invented ways such as music, dance, songs and celebrations that makes the land fertile. The springtime crop-festival that is celebrated among different tribes and non-tribes with different names is a good example of this. In Assam, it is largely known as *Bihu*, in which the music, sound, songs and the dance are designed to attain this result. The sound of the *Dhol* is believed to invoke clouds and rain, the dance is designed to invoke the soil and the songs are designed to invoke love among the performers, because the Assamese folks believed that when women get pregnant, the earth becomes fertile. The similar belief is exercised among other groups of people that reside in Assam and share the same ecological and climatic conditions. Another unique folk-festival is *Bhekulir Biya* (wedding of frogs), performed in a year of drought. This is an elaborate event with proper rituals performed as that of the human wedding rituals. This is performed to invoke rain; Bhekuli being the

symbol for a rainy season. The folks believe that the uniqueness of the marriage will amaze the gods and they will come down to earth to be a part of it.

There are other ceremonies that are performed in Assamese households to shoo off illnesses and epidemics such as pox that are seasonal. This is observed differently among different groups of people, in a household level; mostly known as *Aai Xobah*. There are also folksongs such as *Baromahi geet*, which is found among the people of Northern India also. These are the songs that describe the seasons and the months in a year and the changes in nature in relation to the changes in the day-to-day life especially of a woman. These songs also show the intimate relationship that makes human beings identify themselves with nature. Other folk-songs such as lullabies have immense representation of the surrounding landscape and environment that would create an awe and respect in the minds of the children from the very childhood.

The worldview of the simple folks also influenced the creation of fables and other folktales. In other words, nature was used as examples to store morals and knowledge in folk cultural items. This was done with employing the animals, birds and other natural objects that the particular group of people was familiar with. At times some stereotypes were created out of these natural objects, such as the cunning fox, the fool monkey etc, so that they remain imprinted in the public memory. The transformations from animal or other object to human beings and vice versa, women giving birth to an animal, or an animal giving birth to a human baby, the speaking trees, animals, sun, moon, water etc are some of the popular themes in Assamese folktales. This suggests the close relationship that the folks shared with nature and how they valued and respected this association and passed on the same to the posterity.

These are some of the examples through which human beings' close connections with nature and ecosystem influence folk cultural elements. There are other examples also that exist as attempts to exercise control over the ecosystem. However, the folk-culture does not encourage one to exploit nature. Exploitation and encroachments are examples of modernity. The folk knowledge that is stored in the folklores find expressions mostly as proverbs or folksays. There are several examples of folk instructions to establish household landscapes, for farming, for hunting etc that are found among Assamese folks. For example, the landscaping of a complete household is advised as,

1. *Pube hah, poschime bah*
Uttare guwa, dokhyine dhua
Atiyat kothal, modhye aam
Tehe janiba barir kam

(Poultry on the east, bamboo on the west
 Beetle-nut on the north, toilets on the south
 Jackfruit on the gate, Mango in the middle
 These stand for a prosperous household)

2. *Agbari xuwoni kakini tamule*
Pasbari xuwoni pan.

(Beetlenuts at the front
 Beetle leaves at the rear)

There are others which convey technical knowledge about agriculture and household plantations that would make a household prosperous.

1. *Eibeli banehe ban*
Digholkoi muthi kati
Ukhokoi sang pati
Tate thoi jaba dhan.

(About how one should preserve crops for a flooded year)

2. *Lage tamul nalage*
Nalage tamul lage.
3. *Xate patol, pansot ghon*
Soyt tamul nodon bodon.

Human beings exercise control over nature in taming and domesticating animals too. There are folklores that instruct the selection and taming of animals. (*eg, from the book*)

Fishing songs are activity songs, but the folks also believe that these songs, if sung while fishing among a group, attract the fishes more towards the singer's side. These songs are found mostly in Western and Southern parts of the Nalbari district. In the lower part of Assam there is another interesting festival that is celebrated in the full-moon day of the month of Aghon. This is known as Mohoho or Moh-kheda utsab celebrated to shoo off mosquitoes. On this particular night the young boys of a village go to each house with sticks with which they make some particular sounds that are believed to scare the mosquitoes away. Some tribes name this festival as Bombol Pita utsab. (*eg, from the book*) Thus, human beings decide which objects of the ecosystem around them should be included in or excluded from a human lifestyle.

Folklife in Assam has a huge granary of folklore forms that is pregnant with examples of the man-environment relationship. Citing examples is beyond the limited scope of a paper. The folk-knowledge that has resulted in such folklores is now a major area of research in culture studies. This paper is an introductory attempt to look at Assamese folklore from this point of view. But, without any doubt, there is a larger scope of elaborate research on ecological study of folklore forms of Assam.

References:

Sharma, H.K, 2006, *Asamiya Lokagiti Sanchayan*, Guwahati: Bina Library.

Malik, Syed Abdul, 1992, *Raijor Mukhor Mat*, Guwahati: Students' Stores.

Das, Yogesh, 1972, *Folklore of Assam*, Delhi: National Book Trust.

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cultural_ecology